

Precision robustness testing of a simulation model for energy use in buildings

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Abstract— Software models that simulate the energy performance and behavior of buildings provide experts, engineers and building administrators with a powerful predictive tool that allows users to analyze and predict the future impact of a possible energy saving measure without any costly physical intervention or the need for measurements. To achieve this, models have to be validated and tested for precision robustness, in order to be able to maintain an acceptable predictive capability. The present work deals with the implementation a calculation-based monthly quasi-steady state simulation model for energy use in buildings based on the ISO 13790 standard methodologies and presents its robustness testing methodology.

Keywords— *Building energy model, energy performance of buildings, quasi-steady state energy simulation model, precision robustness testing*

I. INTRODUCTION

Reducing energy consumption is one of the most important priorities in the energy sector worldwide. Putting aside the huge economic benefits gained by reducing the demand for energy, such a reduction also has a huge positive impact on the environment. It is therefore inevitable to assume that there is an ongoing campaign to reduce building energy consumption, since buildings account for 20% of the total energy consumption in the developed world [1].

Such a reduction however requires costly interventions on the building structure and/or systems, making it now more important than ever to have models that can predict the energy performance of buildings. Such software models allow for the user to predict both current and future behavior of a building following a possible energy reducing intervention, making it easier to make a well-informed choice.

As with all software models, there is an inherent degree of uncertainty present when a simulation model for energy use in buildings is implemented. In order to raise this uncertainty, the model must be validated. Model validation comprises of following certain methodologies to verify that the model gives correct results when simulating building energy behavior.

This validation process can be divided into two steps. Firstly, validation is performed against a set of data used as benchmark values. This set can either be derived from standards or can comprise measured real-life values. The second step is to verify that the model behaves in an “acceptable” way when input values are altered or when these values are out of range. This procedure is called model robustness testing and it is a part of the validation process which consists in testing the behavior of a system implementation under exceptional execution conditions in order to check if it still fulfills some robustness requirements [2].

The present work is related with the robustness testing of a monthly quasi-steady state simulation model of building energy consumption based on the ISO 13790 standard [3]. An implementation of this model has already been verified and validated as described in [4]. Further validation of the model is done with reference to model robustness checking and the testing methodology is presented in the following paragraphs.

The paper is organized as follows. Chapter II presents the quasi steady state monthly model, Chapter III presents the model validation in terms of model robustness checking. Chapter IV presents a discussion and conclusions.

II. THE QUASI-STEADY STATE MONTHLY MODEL

The ISO EN 13790 standard describes a complete set of methodologies for the calculation of the energy demand for heating and cooling a building. The method described involves performing energy calculations in a monthly timestep. It is based on a steady state physical model to calculate heating and cooling demands, where the dynamic effects are also taken into account by introducing certain parameters and utilization factors for both heating and cooling calculation [5]. The model referred to in this paper has been implemented in MATLAB environment and has been validated against both the test cases provided in the EN 15265

standard and data from a real hospital. The verification and validation procedure and the corresponding results are presented in [4]. A general outline of the calculation procedure is presented in the following paragraphs.

Apart from the actual building structure, a building also consists of several systems that are closely related to the building operation and effectively its energy efficiency, namely the HVAC system, the lighting system and the appliances. All these systems together with user behavior patterns define the energy performance of the building. The model takes into account every aspect of the building and by introducing a set of input values calculates the energy needed to achieve the necessary internal conditions for users. Using the requirements for these internal conditions the building is divided into thermal zones, which are the basic blocks for the energy calculations.

External conditions are key to the energy need of buildings and are therefore needed as input in the model. Monthly average external temperature and monthly solar irradiance for each combination of orientation and tilt present in building structural elements have to be provided.

The basic equations for the energy calculations, as they are presented in ISO 13790 standard [3], are briefly explained below:

$$Q_{nd(H)} = Q_{ht(H)} - n_{gn(H)}Q_{gn(H)}$$

$$Q_{nd(C)} = Q_{gn(C)} - n_{ls(C)}Q_{ht(C)}$$

Where:

- $Q_{nd(H)}$ and $Q_{nd(C)}$ represent the monthly energy need for heating and cooling the building respectively.
- $Q_{ht(H)}$ and $Q_{ht(C)}$ represent the total heat transfer for the heating and cooling mode respectively
- $Q_{gn(H)}$ and $Q_{gn(C)}$ represent the total heat gains for the heating and cooling mode respectively
- $n_{gn(H)}$ is the gain utilization factor for heating
- $n_{ls(C)}$ is the loss utilization factor for cooling.

The total heat transfer for heating or cooling is divided into heat transfer by transmission (Q_{tr}) and heat transfer by ventilation (Q_{ve}). The first factor depends on building elements construction and is calculated using the following equation:

$$Q_{tr} = H_{tr}(\theta_{int,set} - \theta_e)t$$

The second factor depends on building ventilation and air infiltration and is calculated as follows:

$$Q_{ve} = H_{ve}(\theta_{int,set} - \theta_e)t$$

In the above equations the factors H_{tr} and H_{ve} are overall heat transfer coefficients and are zone dependent. $\theta_{int,set}$ is the internal temperature setpoint and θ_e is the external average monthly temperature. Finally t is the duration of each month in Ms.

The total heat gains are divided into internal heat gains and solar heat gains. Internal heat gains are a summation of heat gains by several sources, namely occupants, lighting, appliances, processes and recoverable losses from hot water and HVAC systems. Solar heat gains represent the heat gains provided by solar radiation and are calculated for every external building structural element.

The two dimensionless utilization factors take into account the fact that just a part of the heat gains and the heat transfer are used for increasing heating or decreasing cooling needs respectively. In this way there is no overestimation of the actual need for heating and/or cooling. A more comprehensive analysis of the quasi steady state model is presented in [5].

The model outputs the monthly energy need for heating and cooling each zone of the building.

III. MODEL ROBUSTNESS CHECKING

Software models that can simulate the energy performance of buildings are essential in the quest for increased energy efficiency. The use of such models can be facilitated in every aspect of a building lifecycle, from the initial design of a new building to valuation of future implementations in an existing and operating structure. This extremely wide spectrum of usage and the ability to experiment with parameters that are difficult or even impossible to control, without the need for costly physical interventions is what makes building energy performance models even more appealing.

For a model to be usable however it must be able to both accurately predict the actual energy performance of a building and to give consistent results. This consistency is validated by performing robustness testing of the model, that is testing the ability of a software to keep an “acceptable” behavior, expressed in terms of robustness requirements, in spite of exceptional or unforeseen

execution conditions (such as the unavailability of system resources, communication failures, invalid or stressful inputs, etc.) [2]. That means that the model has a predictable and consistent behavior under a very wide range of input parameter values and can accurately predict the performance of a building even when these parameters are modified to extreme values.

The present quasi steady state monthly model has been tested for robustness by selecting some parameters from the complete set that is used as input. Selection of variables has been made based on two principles. Firstly, the importance of each variable in the final energy performance of the building was taken into account. The parameters that have the most distinct impact on building energy performance have been selected. Secondly, in order to test the model robustness against the input of “exotic” values, meaning values that are out of range or unrealistic, a couple of parameters has also been selected.

The first list of selected parameters according to their importance in the model is presented below together with a brief description of each parameter and the importance it plays in building energy performance.

1. Heating setpoint [°C] is one of the most important parameters that affects the heating need of a building. Understandably by increasing the heating setpoint the building requires a larger amount of energy to achieve the required internal operating temperature. The heating setpoint was also selected for two more important reasons. Firstly, it is the easiest parameter to change in real life conditions, since it is controlled by thermostats that building users or administrators have access to, making it a prime candidate for a possible intervention. Secondly, apart from energy performance it also affects another critical parameter which is the thermal comfort that users enjoy in the building, making it an even more important aspect of the building operation.
2. Cooling setpoint [°C] is the equivalent of the previous parameter for cooling. All the comments on parameter selection mentioned above apply to the cooling setpoint as well.
3. Thermal transmittance (U value) [W/m²K] of building envelope elements (walls, windows) is a direct measure of the heat transfer rate through a building material. Well insulated elements have low thermal transmittance, which means that there is little exchange of heat between the inside and outside of the building, resulting in fewer losses of energy. The U value affects both heating and cooling mode.
4. Ventilation airflow rate (m³/s) is another extremely important parameter for both heating and cooling modes. It represents the rate in which fresh air is provided from the outside to the inside of the building. This airflow can be both mechanical through a ventilation system or natural through air infiltration that is present in every structure through small gaps in windows. The importance of ventilation in the total energy needs of a building increases when the air enters the building untreated, that is when the air has the same temperature as the external environment.
5. Lighting loads (W) have a dual importance. Firstly lighting presents significant internal gains inside the building which lower the heating and increase the cooling needs. Secondly lighting represents an important part of the electrical consumption of a building, especially in buildings that have the need for round the clock lighting like medical centers. For these reasons replacing the lighting with new technology luminaires is one of the most common interventions in old structures.

Besides from the subset of parameters presented above a couple more were selected as parameters that cannot be physically altered but have an impact on building energy performance:

1. Building orientation affects energy performance through altering the energy gains from solar radiation. More building elements facing south increase solar gains.
2. Building location is the best example of an “exotic” parameter since altering it is equal to moving the building to a different location with different external conditions (external temperature and solar irradiation).

By uniting the two subsets above we get a total of seven parameters for robustness testing. The values of these parameters have been altered during the simulations according to the following ranges:

These input variables have taken different values in the following ranges:

- Heating setpoints {+0, +1, +2, -1, -2} degrees
- Cooling setpoints {+0, +1, +2, -1, -2} degrees
- U values {+0%, +30%, -30%}
- Ventilation requirements {+0%, +50%}
- Lighting loads {+0%, -50%}
- Building orientation {+0, +90, -90} degrees

- Building location {Palermo, Paris}

This selection provides a total of 450 cases that were simulated to test model robustness.

The model provides monthly energy need for heating and cooling as results.

The building structure that has been selected for testing is the single space volume that is presented in the test cases of EN 15265 standard. The same single space volume and test cases have been used to validate the model, as presented in [4].

Fig. 1. EN 15265 single space for testing

For testing purposes each of the 450 cases is simulated both in the ISO 13790 static model implementation and in an interconnected EnergyPlus dynamic simulator which is used as benchmark [6]. This EnergyPlus model has been presented in [7].

Comparison between the results from both models is done by using the metric provided in both the ISO 13790 Annex H and the EN 15265 [8] standards, which is the percentage of heating or cooling monthly energy needs difference between each test case and the basic simulation that refers to the original building, with reference to total heating and cooling yearly energy needs of the original building for EnergyPlus and ISO 13790 implementation.

Results of the robustness testing are presented below for selected test cases. The simulation cases that are presented represent the worst scenarios in which the biggest differences between EnergyPlus and the ISO model occur. The percentage depicted in all figures is the difference observed in both models between the basic simulation case and the specific test case presented.

When altering Heating and Cooling Set-points while keeping all the other parameters in their original values the biggest total annual energy need difference between EnergyPlus and ISO model is observed when both the heating and cooling setpoints are reduced by 2°C, with the difference standing at 12.57% for the ISO model. Figures 2-4 show the difference percentage on Heating needs, Cooling needs, and overall Energy needs between building basic simulation and the particular case. Figure 5 shows the average monthly difference between EnergyPlus and ISO model for all cases when altering setpoints only.

Fig. 2. Difference percentage of heating needs between test case and base case in EnergyPlus and ISO model (heating setpoint -2 degrees, cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 3. Difference percentage of cooling needs between test case and base case in EnergyPlus and ISO model (heating setpoint -2 degrees, cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 4. Difference percentage of total energy needs between test case and base case in EnergyPlus and ISO model (heating setpoint -2 degrees, cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 5. Average monthly difference percentage between ISO and EnergyPlus for 25 cases (altering setpoints while all other variables remain constant)

When changing the U value of the entire building by +30% the difference in total energy for the ISO model is 5.13% while the worst case when altering setpoints at the same time is 12.67% (heating and cooling setpoints -2 degrees, U value +30%). Figures 6-8 show the influence of this variable on heating and cooling needs as calculated by EnergyPlus and ISO 13790 when U values are changed by +30% and heating and cooling setpoints are changed by -2 degrees each. Figure 9 shows the average monthly difference between EnergyPlus and ISO model for all cases when altering setpoints and U value is changed by +30%.

Fig. 6. Difference percentage of heating needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (U factor +30%, heating and cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 7. Difference percentage of cooling needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (U factor +30%, heating and cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 8. Difference percentage of total energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (U factor +30%, heating and cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 9. Average monthly difference percentage between ISO and EnergyPlus for 25 cases (altering setpoints while U value is changed by +30% and all other variables remain constant)

When changing the U value in the opposite direction by -30% the relevant graphs for heating and cooling as well as total energy needs for EnergyPlus and ISO 13790 implementation are shown below in Figures 10-13.

Fig. 10. Difference percentage of heating needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (U factor -30%, heating and cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 11. Difference percentage of cooling needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (U factor -30%, heating and cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 12. Difference percentage of total energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (U factor -30%, heating and cooling setpoint -2 degrees)

Fig. 13. Average monthly difference percentage between ISO and EnergyPlus for 25 cases (altering setpoints while U value is changed by -30% and all other variables remain constant)

With reference to lighting, a scenario of -50% decrease is assessed. When coupled with a decrease of 30% in the U value, heating setpoint increase of +2 and cooling setpoint decrease of -2 degrees the Heating, Cooling and total energy needs for EnergyPlus and ISO implementation are produced and presented in Figures 14-16.

Fig. 14. Difference percentage of heating needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (Lighting -50%, U value -30%, heating setpoint +2, cooling setpoint -2)

Fig. 15. Difference percentage of cooling needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (Lighting -50%, U value -30%, heating setpoint +2, cooling setpoint -2)

Fig. 16. Difference percentage of total energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (Lighting -50%, U value -30%, heating setpoint +2, cooling setpoint -2)

When ventilation airflow rate is increased by 50% while all other parameters remain the same, the following graphs of the Heating, Cooling and Total Energy needs are produced (Figures 17-19).

Fig. 17. Difference percentage of heating needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (ventilation +50%)

Fig. 18. Difference percentage of cooling needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (ventilation +50%)

Fig. 19. Difference percentage of total energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (ventilation +50%)

When orientation is changed by -90 degrees (from West to South) the following graphs of the Heating, Cooling and Total Energy needs are produced (Figures 20-22).

Fig. 20. Difference percentage of heating energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (orientation -90 degrees)

Fig. 21. Difference percentage of cooling energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (orientation -90 degrees)

Fig. 22. Difference percentage of total energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO model (orientation -90 degrees)

The simulation and model execution campaign resulted in a demonstration of a maximum absolute value of this metric equal to 7.86%.

A snapshot of the error graph for the setpoint subset output is depicted in figure 23, followed by the snapshot of the worst case difference in the total annual consumption, expressed in total, heating and cooling loads (Figures 24-26).

Fig. 23. Difference percentage of monthly per total year energy needs between EnergyPlus and ISO for 25 combinations of setpoint subset

Fig. 24. Total energy needs for heating and cooling (worst-case scenario – heating setpoint +1°C / cooling setpoint +2°C / orientation North)

Fig. 25. Energy needs for heating (worst-case scenario – heating setpoint +1°C / cooling setpoint +2°C / orientation North)

Fig. 26. Energy needs for cooling (worst-case scenario – heating setpoint +1°C / cooling setpoint +2°C / orientation North)

IV. DISCUSSION

This paper presents the precision robustness testing of a building energy efficiency quasi steady state monthly simulation model based on the EN 13790 standard. The presented model is extendable to any building of whatever size and complexity, since the calculation procedure is not dependent on type or quantity of input data. By entering the appropriate input values, the model can simulate the energy performance of any structure.

In order to test precision robustness of the model, the EnergyPlus simulation is regarded as a benchmark. From the complete set of parameters that exist in the model a small subset has been selected. These parameters are then modified within a well defined range of values. This results in a total of 450 simulation cases, a number deemed adequate for the purpose of testing the model precision robustness.

For the needs of the precision robustness testing the single volume defined in the EN 15265 standard is used. The same volume has been created in EnergyPlus so that simulations can be executed in both models, and the results can be compared to assess the influence of each parameter in the model outcome.

In order to compare the results between the static and the dynamic models the metric defined in Annex H of the ISO 13790 standard has been used. This metric is described as the heating or cooling energy needs different expressed as a percentage of the total heating and cooling needs of the building.

Results show that during the entire simulation the chosen metric takes a maximum value of 7.86%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the deviation between the two models is within acceptable limits, verifying robustness check of the ISO 13790 static model.

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